

Making Medicine Material: Objects and Materiality in the History of Medicine

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Abstract

This positioning paper surveys recent historical scholarship on objects and material culture relating to health and medicine. Analyzing scholarship under four main themes—professional medicine; everyday health; spaces, places, and environments; and consumption, globalism, and colonialism—the paper demonstrates the vibrancy and breadth of the field; it outlines how scholarship across these themes has viewed a wide range of objects and forms of materiality as not only integral to medical knowledge and health practices in the past but has often uncovered alternative, subversive, and multiple ways of knowing and doing that are inaccessible by the written word alone. The paper ends by providing possible future directions for scholars keen to further explore the role of materiality in medical knowledge making and practice. In particular, it suggests how scholars might fruitfully expand the material categories they work with, adopt “material time” and include more critical self-awareness in their research.

Keywords: medicine, health, materiality, objects, material culture

The “material turn” has had a considerable impact on the discipline of history in recent years, the history of medicine included. Over the past twenty years or so, there have been countless histories of health, healing, and medicine that have addressed aspects of the material world. Indeed, materiality is now so embedded in the discipline that a recently published six-volume cultural history of medicine spanning the past 2,500 years has included chapters on “objects,” the first of its kind in disciplinary specific compendia.¹ This is not to say that historians of medicine previously ignored materiality, but it is noticeable how the material history of medicine has gathered pace in the twenty-first century. Accordingly, we now have a wealth of studies of materials—including those of “natural” origin and those man- and machine-made—and objects made from or composed of these materials within what

¹ Roger Cooter, ed., *A Cultural History of Medicine*, vols. 1–6 (London: Bloomsbury, 2021).

might be called material cultures consisting of a variety of things and people within an assortment of places and spaces.

This essay provides a survey of recent work on medical objects and the material cultures of which they form a part, demonstrating its significance for the field. While the sheer number of materially oriented studies demonstrates the field's vibrancy, space limitations here necessitate selection. The essay thus pays particular attention to studies that seek to integrate materiality into discussions of ways of knowing and doing.² Emerging as a branch of the history of ideas in the nineteenth century, the history of medicine has long acknowledged that objects and materials embody knowledge, particularly in the Western world since the Enlightenment. But the relatively recent influence of approaches from beyond the field, from science and technology studies (STS), cultural history, and material culture studies, for example, has allowed historians interested in medicine and health to draw on materiality as a way of investigating the social construction of different forms of knowledge and the myriad ways that knowledge, associated practices, experiences, and identities informed each other.³

History of medicine's embrace of material approaches from other disciplines has not always extended to the adoption of material-focused methods. While some recent studies have effectively drawn on the evidence provided by the physical properties of objects and materials, particularly those focused on premodern eras and non-Western cultures where there is an absence of written documentation, the reliance on texts, the centrality of discourse, and the use of objects and materials as illustrative endures.⁴ Unlike scholars in disciplines like anthropology and the history of science, close attention is not often paid to the "thingness" of an object/material within the history of

2 There are many other approaches to materiality not discussed here. For example, I have discussed material practices using historical enactment elsewhere. See Claire L. Jones, "Surgical Instruments: History and Historiography," in *The Palgrave Handbook of the History of Surgery*, ed. Thomas Schlich (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2018), 235–57. For more on ways of knowing and doing, see John V. Pickstone, *Ways of Knowing: A New History of Science, Technology and Medicine* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2000); Pamela H. Smith, Amy R. W. Meyers, and Harold J. Cook, eds., *Ways of Making and Knowing: The Material Culture of Empirical Knowledge* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2017).

3 Ludmilla Jordanova, "The Social Construction of Medical Knowledge," in *Locating Medical History: Their Stories and Their Meanings*, ed. Frank Huisman and John Harley Warner (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2004), 338–63.

4 Studies of the differing designs of Roman surgical instruments and pharmaceutical jars from the Middle Ages, for example, have provided insights into Roman surgery and the cultural context about the justification of the use of certain drugs, respectively. For example, Lawrence J. Bliquez, *The Tools of Asclepius: Surgical Implements in Greek and Roman Times* (Leiden: Brill, 2014). For exemplary non-health-focused studies on the use of materiality to uncover the lives of people who left no records, see Toby Green, *A Fistful of Shells: West Africa from the Rise of the Slave Trade to the Age of Revolution* (London: Penguin, 2020); Tiya Miles, *All That She Carried: The Journey of Ashley's Sack, a Black Family Keepsake* (Profile, 2024).

medicine; here, it is the human subject (often practitioner or patient) that makes knowledge embodied in and practiced with the object/material.⁵

But materials, objects, and the material cultures they constitute can be as important as texts and language; alongside texts, materials and objects can provide us with more comprehensive answers to familiar questions, as well as broadening the questions we ask. Recognizing, as material culture scholars do, that materials, objects, and their cultures are dynamic and dependent on the interpretative contexts of time and place, and that materiality is an ongoing process, not a static state of being, can be a powerful way to uncover alternative, subversive, and multiple medical and nonmedical ways of knowing and doing.⁶ For example, a knife made in Sheffield from surgical steel for a late nineteenth-century surgeon might enable us to tell concomitant narratives about the professional acceptance of asepsis, the global significance of Sheffield as a site of cutlery production, the patient's perspective of surgery and, when used, the site of operation; evidence of the knife's use through a worn blade and its repair through a replacement handle in the mid-twentieth century could invoke a story of the sustained popularity of aseptic surgery and the industry behind repurposing instruments, but it might also tell us more about the more mundane and repetitive embodied activities of instrument repair and cutting into human flesh; the knife's later twentieth-century fall into disuse may enable us to examine the replacement of open with key hole surgery, but its acquisition by a museum may also reveal insights into the wider social practices of object collecting and curatorship. With meanings of objects multiple, relational, and always in flux, the potential of material approaches to provide new insights into the history of medicine is therefore vast.

In what follows then, I outline how histories of medicine and health in the Western tradition have drawn on aspects of materiality in relation to knowledge in four main sections: professional medicine; everyday health; spaces, places, and environments; and consumption, globalism, and colonialism. To end, I outline some possible future directions for historians of medicine keen to further explore the role of materiality in knowledge making and practice.

Tools of Professional Medicine: Knowledge, Authority, and Negotiation

5 For material studies in anthropology and the history of science, see, for example, Igor Kopytoff, "The Cultural Biography of Things," in *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective*, ed. Arjun Appadurai (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986): 64–91; Lorraine Daston, ed., *Biographies of Scientific Objects* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000); Daston, ed., *Things That Talk: Object Lessons from Art and Science* (New York: Zone Books, 2004).

6 For example, Daniel Miller, ed., *Material Cultures: Why Some Things Matter* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1997); Carl Knappett, *Thinking through Material Culture: An Interdisciplinary Perspective* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2005).

Histories of orthodox Western medicine are among the most common to draw on specific forms of materiality to provide new perspectives on knowledge. Indeed, focus on tools, instruments, appliances, technologies, and machines remains common not only because medicine is replete with them, but because they have been integral to the field's practice of scientific medicine and its professional status since its foundation. Late nineteenth-century aseptic tools seemingly unproblematically embodied bacteriology, for example. Yet, while such objects, produced in ever-increasing numbers, were once seen to epistemologically drive scientific medicine, history of medicine's recent incorporation first of the "social" (an agency-centered approach), then of the "practical" (an approach that explored what those with agency did), and then of the "material" (that explored what those with agency did with what) has positioned technologies as value-laden objects that were accepted, rejected, developed, and used within professional networks and wider technical, social, cultural, and economic contexts.⁷ Rather than being seen as the product of pioneers in possession of some universal scientific "truth," historians of medicine began to see technologies as "fashioned" and medical authority "negotiated" within a variety of local, national, and international cultures involving instrument makers, institutions, patients, and the state, among others.⁸

Accordingly, we now have more historically contingent studies of medical technologies, ranging from eighteenth-century anatomical specimens to twentieth-century straightjackets and even cats and leeches.⁹ Historiography

7 Michael Worboys, "Practice and Science of Medicine in the Nineteenth Century," *Isis* 102 (2011): 109–15. A pioneering history of science on the importance of objects in the production of early scientific and medical knowledge without a teleology is Steven Shapin and Simon Schaffer, *Leviathan and the Air-Pump: Hobbes, Boyle, and the Experimental Life* (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1985).

8 The literature on medical technologies that take such a perspective is extensive, but some notable examples include Thomas Schlich and Christopher Crenner, eds., *Technological Change in Modern Surgery: Historical Perspectives on Innovation* (Rochester, N.Y.: University of Rochester Press, 2017); Thomas Schlich, "Negotiating Technologies in Surgery: The Controversy about Surgical Gloves in the 1890s," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 87, no. 2 (2013): 170–97; Shelley McKellar, *Artificial Hearts: The Allure and Ambivalence of a Controversial Medical Technology* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2018); Jennifer Wallis, "Bloody Technology: The Sphygmograph in Asylum Practice," *Hist. Psychiatry* 28 (2017): 297–310; Carsten Timmerman and Julie Anderson, eds., *Devices and Designs: Medical Technologies in Historical Perspectives* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2006); Christelle Rabier, ed., "Fitting for Health," special issue of *Technol. Cult.* 54, no. 3 (2013), see "Introduction: The Crafting of Medicine in the Early Industrial Age," 437–59; Stuart Blume, *Insight and Industry: The Dynamics of Technological Change in Medicine* (Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press, 1992).

9 For example, L. Dacome, *Malleable Anatomies: Models, Makers, and Material Culture in Eighteenth-Century Italy* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017); Rina Knoeff and Robert Zwijnenberg, eds., *The Fate of Anatomical Collections* (London: Routledge, 2015); B. Majerus, "Material Objects in Twentieth Century History of Psychiatry," *BMGN: Low Countries Hist. Rev.* 132, no. 1 (2017): 149–69; Sarah Chaney, "Psychiatry's Material Culture: The Symbolic Power of the Straightjacket," in *Sources in the History of Psychiatry, from 1800 to the Present*, ed. Chris Millard and Jennifer Wallis (London: Routledge, 2022), 2–18; Projit Bihari Mukharji, "Cat and Mouse: Animal Technologies, Trans-imperial Networks and Public Health from Below, British India, c. 1907–1918," *Soc. Hist. Med.* 31, no. 3 (2017): 510–32; Rob G. W. Kirk and Neil Pemberton, "Re-

on the stethoscope provides a good example of this shift in perspective. While early historians viewed the first stethoscope of 1816 as crucial for ushering in medicine's epistemological transformation because it allowed practitioners to identify internal signs of ill health and disease, late twentieth-century critics argued that this shift to pathological anatomy enabled and signified by the stethoscope fostered medicine's objectifying gaze. Meanings attached to the stethoscope shifted and it became a coercive instrument of professional power, acting as a physical buffer between practitioner and patient and allowing patient objectification and medicine's wider societal dominance.¹⁰ Indeed, the stethoscope was viewed not simply as a tool of auscultation, but as central to the transformation of the medical practitioner into a powerful professional in both medical and popular cultures.¹¹ However, more recent studies suggest that the stethoscope was neither solely an embodiment of scientific progress nor a symbol of professional control. For example, in the context of early twentieth-century Bengal, Projit Bihari Mukharji demonstrates that the stethoscope was adopted into modern Ayurveda because it suited the aims of both sides of a divided medical profession (purists and syncretists).¹² Caroline Avery argues that in nineteenth-century Britain professional acceptance of the stethoscope was not solely due to increased understandings of disease or acoustics, but was instead due to the fact that new stethoscope designs accounted for portability and comfort when used.¹³ The extensive number of studies on the cadaver as a prime but different type of medical object demonstrate how modern and early modern medical knowledge was made through practice.¹⁴ Transformed from human subject to medical object through the often-experimental processes of dissection, fragmentation, mounting, and display, the cadaver became a tool

imagining Bleeders: The Medical Leech in the Nineteenth Century Bloodletting Encounter," *Med. Hist.* 55, no. 3 (2011): 355–60.

10 Erwin H. Ackerknecht, *Medicine at the Paris Hospital, 1794–1848* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1967); Michel Foucault, *The Birth of the Clinic: An Archaeology of Medical Perception*, trans. A. Sheridan (London: Routledge, 1973); Stanley J. Reiser, *Medicine and the Reign of Technology* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1978). See also Cornelius Borck, "Objects," in *A Cultural History of Medicine in the Modern Age*, ed. Todd Meyers (London: Bloomsbury, 2021), 109–32, 113.

11 Lawrence J. Hergott, "Aspects of Ending a Lifelong Dream," *JAMA* 317, no. 2 (2017): 137–38; Tom Rice, "The Hallmark of a Doctor": The Stethoscope and the Making of Medical Identity," *J. Material Cult.* 15, no. 3 (2010): 287–301; Claire Wendland, "This Thing, a Stethoscope," in *Making Sense of Medicine: Material Culture and the Reproduction of Medical Knowledge*, ed. John Nott and Anna Harris (Bristol: Intellect Books, 2022); Borck, "Objects" (n. 10), 110.

12 Projit Bihari Mukharji, "Akarnan: The Stethoscope and Making of Modern Ayurveda, Bengal, c. 1894–1952," *Technol. Cult.* 60, no. 4 (2019): 953–78.

13 Caroline L. Avery, "Importing the Stethoscope: The Uptake of Mediate Auscultation by British Practitioners, 1816–1850" (Ph.D. diss., University of Leeds, 2020).

14 For example, Ruth Richardson, *Death, Dissection and the Destitute* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000); Michael Sappol, *A Traffic in Human Bodies: Anatomy and Embodied Social Identity in Nineteenth-Century America* (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 2004); Katherine Park, *Secrets of Women: Gender, Generation, and the Origins of Human Dissection* (New York: Zone Books, 2006); Elizabeth Hallam, *Anatomy Museum: Death and the Body Displayed* (London: Reaktion Books, 2016).

unlike the stethoscope. While the stethoscope was created and subsequently used according to specific anatomical and pathological principles, the processes that created cadavers meant that knowledge making in the dissection room, the lecture and Anatomy Theater, and museum relied on doing. Only through these practices could the corpse become “an epistemic object” and a “problematic text” to be studied.¹⁵ New knowledge was thus acquired through each process; this ongoing transformation of material, knowledge, and practice explains why cadavers have been of such interest to material culture scholars, who view materiality as a process.

But anatomy and pathology were not the only forms of knowledge constructed through interactions with the cadaver. While the skin, muscle, bone, brain, and fluids of patients within the Victorian asylum were central to psychiatric thought and asylum practice, they also represented patient experience of illnesses and asylum doctor identity.¹⁶ At late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century medical schools across America, dissected bodies aided the forging of new identities among medical students. Posing with a cadaver, often black and sometimes female, was an important rite of passage for white students keen to demonstrate their medical skills and superior social position; in turn, poses were captured in a photograph, another object, and sometimes memorialized in others: the postcard, *carte de visite*, or greeting card.¹⁷

Through other tools, negotiations over medical knowledge and its authority were also gendered. Studies of early modern obstetric forceps, for example, demonstrate the tool’s symbolism of increasing male midwife intervention into what had been the female practice of childbirth and the simultaneous loss of female midwife power.¹⁸ In late nineteenth-century America, nurses embraced and rejected different technologies not necessarily because they embodied the most up-to-date medical knowledge but because they enhanced their own visibility and professional autonomy amid male medical monopoly.¹⁹

Practices represented authority and transformed body parts, transforming knowledge. Other technologies too were crucial in producing new racist forms of knowledge and practice. The spirometer, to measure lung capacity, was developed in the 1840s as a response to Victorian anxieties about the impact of industrialization and urbanization on working-class bodies, but imported into

15 Francesco Paolo de Ceglia, *The Body of Evidence: Corpses and Proofs in Early Modern European Medicine* (Leiden: Brill, 2020), 3, 15.

16 Jennifer Wallis, *Investigating the Body in the Victorian Asylum: Doctors, Patients, and Practices* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017).

17 John Harley Warner and James M. Edmonson, *Dissection: Photographs of a Rite of Passage in American Medicine, 1880–1930* (New York: Blast Books, 2009).

18 Adrian Wilson, “Midwifery and the ‘Medical Marketplace,’” in *Medicine and the Market in England and Its Colonies, c. 1450–c.1850*, ed. Mark S. R. Jenner and Patrick Wallis (Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave, 2007), 153–74; Wilson, *The Making of Man-Midwifery: Childbirth in England, 1660–1770* (1995; repr., London: UCL Press, 2018).

19 Margarete Sandelowski, *Devices and Desires: Gender, Technology, and American Nursing* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2000).

the United States soon after, it was used to “prove” that “Blacks” had had less lung capacity than “whites,” a social construction that endured throughout the twentieth century across different contexts.²⁰ And as Keith Wailoo has explained, blood technologies “as knowledge-producing” tools aided both the emergence and disappearance of chlorosis, a nineteenth-century disorder that mainly afflicted young girls, and the twentieth-century construction of “Negro blood” and “hemoglobinopathy” in sickle cell anemia.²¹ With a broad definition of blood technologies, Wailoo addresses new drugs, clinical facilities, and formalized research protocols, such as randomized clinical trials, in addition to devices like the hemocytometer. Wailoo’s “technological system” is analogous to Thomas Schlich’s more recent “network of control” within the nineteenth-century operating theater.²² Here, Schlich considers how, together, gloves, lights, operating tables, anatomy atlases, anesthetics, and aseptic instruments allowed surgeons to maintain efficacy and safety in surgical procedures that were becoming less conservative and more complicated and intricate.

To be sure, Wailoo and Schlich (and others who focus on medical tools) continue to emphasize human, rather than object, agency in conceptualizing technologies in networks and systems. Indeed, unlike new materialist theories, such as Bruno Latour’s infamous actor-network theory (ANT), which sought to break down human-nonhuman binaries as a rejection of anthropocentrism and the postmodern reduction of everything to dis-course, historians of medicine rarely propose that objects have agency.²³ It is through technologies, tools, bodies, and an amalgamation of those objects that surgeons maintained efficacy and safety, and hematologists, asylum doctors, and medical students shaped disease identities, as well as their own.

Objects of Lay Knowledge, Everyday Health, and Well-Being

The examples outlined above are emblematic of a human-centric approach to the history of medical technologies. Human use of technologies, and materials more broadly, to demonstrate thought and action extends beyond

20 Lundy Braun, *Breathing Race into the Machine: The Surprising Career of the Spirometer from Plantation to Genetics* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2014).

21 Keith Wailoo, *Drawing Blood: Technology and Disease Identity in Twentieth Century America* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1997), vii, 30, 136.

22 Schlich, “Negotiating Technologies in Surgery” (n. 8); Thomas Schlich and Christopher Crenner, “Technological Change in Surgery: An Introductory Essay,” in Schlich and Crenner, *Technological Change in Modern Surgery* (n. 8).

23 Bruno Latour, *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network Theory* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005). See also Tim Ingold, “Rethinking the Animate, Re-animating Thought,” *Ethnos* 71, no. 1 (2006): 9–20. For a new materialist approach to cadavers, see Anu Salmela, “Fleshy Stories: New Materialism and Female Suicides in Late Nineteenth-Century Finland,” *Hist. Cult. Mod.* 6, no. 1 (2018).

professional medicine, and as studies focused on lay objects and materials have suggested, no technology, object, or material is medical as such but is imbued with medical meanings through ongoing interactions with medical practitioners, while alternative meanings are imbued through other associations. A medieval or early modern urinal could be both a tool of the medical practitioner as well as a domestic item stored under a middle-class bed. Medieval and early modern vessels for prepping and storing medicines, materials like mercury and copper, precious stones like jet and coral, and objects like cosmetics and tweezers used to pluck hair could imbue multiple medical and nonmedical meanings depending on their users and contexts.²⁴ Billiard tables, boules, and pall mall mallets in an early modern Italy home could represent entertainment or the pursuit of a healthy lifestyle through moderate physical exercise.²⁵ In suggesting that the “medical” itself was a social construction, research on nonmedical objects and materials has highlighted how knowledge and expertise (and thus power and agency) over health and healing could be in hands of nonprofessionals, and that accordingly, the boundaries between professional and lay medicine could be blurred.

Of course, the recent focus on everyday objects and materials in the early modern period can be partly explained by the blurred boundaries between lay and professional medicine itself until at least the mid-nineteenth century when professional state-sanctioned monopolization occurred, but such focus is also reflective of the scholarly interests of those who undertake such studies. Recent early modern histories of medicine have often centered on how health-related objects formed part of the broader social and cultural lives of the actors under study, rather than the professional lives of doctors. This broadening up of the medical world of objects to “small things” has extended the range of historical actors seen to be involved in medical work so that ordinary men, women, and children, craftsmen, retailers, and others often absent from the historical record are viewed as both practitioners and receivers of health care. So, while professional meanings and uses of objects/materials are addressed, it is commonly in conjunction with the wider role of materials and objects in everyday life. The following three diverse examples highlight how objects/materials embodied lay knowledge of health, healing, and well-being, alongside or in opposition to professional medical knowledge. The first example is the wealth of studies that have emerged in recent years on the material culture of early modern fertility, pregnancy, childbirth, and childcare. In the context of nineteenth-century France, objects of childcare, including cribs and toys, have been straightforwardly identified as embodiments of new

24 Theresa Tyers, “‘Trotule (Trotula) Puts Many Things on to Decorate and Embellish the Fact but I Intend Solely to Remove Infection’: L’Abbé Poutrel and His *Chirurgie* c.1300 in Context,” in *Approaching Facial Difference: Past and Present*, ed. Patricia Skinner and Emily Cock (London: Bloomsbury, 2018), 177–91.

25 Sandra Cavallo and Teresa Storey, *Healthy Living in Late Renaissance Italy* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013).

(often medically endorsed) sleeping norms and contemporary theories of psychological attachment.²⁶ But early modern nonprofessional objects related to fertility, pregnancy, and childbirth held other meanings for women and their families. For example, Jacqueline Musacchio has explored how everyday goods consumed by well-to-do Italians of the Renaissance, ranging from painted bowls and trays to paintings, were both useful for childbirth but also highly symbolic. While acknowledging the importance of medical ideas of maternal impression embedded in images viewed by pregnant women, Musacchio examines how clothing worn by the mother and the furnishings for the confinement room—embroidered sheets, pillows, tablecloths, and birthing chairs—were intended to be seen by the female visitors who came to pay their respects on the birth of a child and aimed to demonstrate the wealth and social standing of the family. Painted wooden birth trays suggested concerns about the continuation of lineage, while sacred and secular paintings of birth aimed to encourage both devotion and mothering.²⁷

Others have identified the importance of talismans, gems, and other stones, including the eagle stone, which was favored for nearly two centuries and across the social classes for its perceived efficacy in facilitating childbirth and protecting pregnancy. The stone was not only systematically included in doctors' writings but also a common feature of the recipe books, herbals, and other new books that were becoming a standard component of middle-class domestic libraries.²⁸ Current research on coral too highlights the importance of jewelry and other domestic and decorative items made from the substance within the lower-class as well as middle- to upper-class family.²⁹ Women's use of stones was also evidence of how belief in the divine (and not contemporary medicine) worked as a method of healing in the early modern world.

The second example is objects of disability. Corrective or assistive devices, both attachable to the body like prostheses and those standalone like walking

26 Gal Ventura, "Jean Monet Sleeping: Medicalisation, Dreams and Transitional Objects," *Soc. Hist. Med.* 36, no. 1 (February 2023): 80–109. The concept of transitional objects emerged from Donald Winnicott, the mid-twentieth-century British psychoanalyst, and his observations that a baby's emotional development is always in relation to the primary object (mother).

27 Jacqueline Marie Musacchio, *The Art and Ritual of Childbirth in Renaissance Italy* (New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Press, 1999). See also Rebecca Whiteley, "Prayer, Pregnancy and Print," in *Religion and Life Cycles in Early Modern England*, ed. Caroline Bowden, Emily Vine, and Tessa Whitehouse (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2021), 40–64.

28 Sandra Cavallo, "Objects," in *A Cultural History of Medicine in the Renaissance*, ed. Elaine Leong and Claudia Stein (New York: Bloomsbury, 2022), 111–39; Nichola E. Harris, "Loadstones Are a Girl's Best Friend: Lapidary Cures, Midwives, and Manuals of Popular Healing in Medieval and Early Modern England," in *The Sacred and the Secular in Medieval Healing: Sites, Objects, and Texts*, ed. Barbara S. Bowers and Linda Migl Keyser (Abingdon: Routledge, 2017); Marieke Hendriksen, "The Repudiation and Persistence of Lapidary Medicine in Eighteenth-Century Dutch Medicine and Pharmacy," in *Gems in the Early Modern World: Materials, Knowledge and Global Trade, 1450–1800*, ed. Michael Bycroft and Sven Dupré Bycroft (Berlin: Springer, 2019); Martha Baldwin, "Toads and Plague: Amulet Therapy in Seventeenth-Century Medicine," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 67, no. 2 (1993): 227–47.

29 Francesca Richards, "Medicine, Charm or Treasure? Mediterranean Red Coral in England, 1600–1800" (Ph.D. diss., University of Kent, forthcoming).

sticks and wheelchairs, have been the subject of much recent scholarship due to the fact that disability is viewed as unique in the extent to which it is bonded with technologies as a medium of social interaction.³⁰ As such scholarship demonstrates, forms of social interaction with such devices are various and could include those between medical practitioner and patient, whereby devices could embody and produce medical knowledge aimed at “fixing” the impaired body and allow patients to conform to the medicalized, industrialized, and commercialized contexts of the eighteenth, nineteenth, and twentieth centuries in order to carry out employment and hide visible deformities in polite society.³¹

But social interactions could also go beyond the medical. Through their specific materials and design features, devices could embody artisanal and commercial knowledge and demonstrate craftsman, company, surgeon, and user cocreation, allowing users to conduct everyday functional tasks and shaping interactions with friends, families, and local communities.³² Charles West demonstrates how in early medieval northern France a prosthetic hand buried with a man in his forties or fifties who experienced double amputation highlights the inclusive nature of the local community that provided him with his prosthetic and allowed him to conduct everyday tasks.³³ Heidi Hausse’s recent book on hand prostheses provides a detailed account of the importance of artisanal knowledge in shaping disability in early modern Germany. Focusing on ratchets and springs as particular features of these prostheses, Hausse demonstrates that it was clockmakers, armorers, and woodworkers, and not surgeons, who possessed the required mechanical knowledge to produce an array of prosthetic hands between the 1500s and 1700s for well-to-do amputee patrons. She shows how these prostheses were not only repositories of mechanical knowledge but also active in influencing surgeons’ ideas about amputation and prostheses over this two-hundred-year period. Drawing on

30 Katherine Ott, “Disability Things: Material Culture and American Disability History, 1700–2010,” in *Disability Histories*, ed. Susan Birch and Michael Rembis (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2014), 119–62; Coreen A. McGuire, “What Is Disability History the History Of?,” *Hist. Compass* 22, no. 6 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1111/hic3.12813>; Katherine Ott, David Serlin, and Stephen Mihm, eds., *Artificial Parts, Practical Lives: Modern Histories of Prosthetics* (New York: New York University Press, 2002).

31 David M. Turner and Alun Withey, “Technologies of the Body: Polite Consumption and the Correction of Deformity in Eighteenth-Century England,” *History* 99, no. 5 (December 2014): 775–96; Claire L. Jones, ed., *Rethinking Prostheses in Anglo-American Commodity Cultures* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2017); B. Curtis and S. Thompson, “‘A Plentiful Crop of Cripples Made by All This Progress’: Disability, Artificial Limbs and Working-Class Mutualism in the South Wales Coalfield, 1890–1948,” *Soc. Hist. Med.* 27 (2014): 708–27; Vanessa Warne, “‘To Invest a Cripple with Peculiar Interest’: Artificial Legs and Upper-Class Amputees at Mid-century,” *Victorian Rev.* 35, no. 2 (2009): 83–100.

32 Elizabeth Guffey and Bess Williamson, eds., *Making Disability Modern: Design Histories* (New York: Bloomsbury, 2020); Jaipreet Viridi, “Material Traces of Disability: Andrew Gawley’s Steel Hands,” *Nuncius* 35, no. 3 (2020): 606–31.

33 Charles West, “Radical Object: An Early Medieval Prosthetic Hand,” *Hist. Workshop*, September 26, 2022, <https://www.historyworkshop.org.uk/disability-history/radical-object-an-early-medieval-prosthetic-hand/>.

Pamela Smith's important work on early modern artisans like potters, sculptors, and goldsmiths, *Hausse* demonstrates how knowledge is not only constructed in the act of making but made by artisans and laborers, the type of lay or "invisible" actors increasingly given agency in histories of medicine and science.³⁴

Well-worn and repaired devices could also indicate user acceptance, resistance, adaptation, and emotional attachment to them, as well as user identities and life experiences as performative knowledge. For example, extant objects in museum collections suggest that Victorian users could add materials such as pads of "felt-like material" to the arms of their spectacles in order to improve the comfort of the frame on the skin or to reduce pressure, and create drawstring bags embossed with flowers to contain and carry their hearing trumpets.³⁵ One female Indian user added toe rings and henna patterns to her foot prosthesis, highlighting the significance of gendered design preferences situated in specific cultural contexts.³⁶

Uncovering such multilayered forms of social interaction with disability devices not only has allowed historians to overcome, or at least challenge, the well-established binary of social/medical models of disability and even the separation between disability history and the history of medicine, but also has demonstrated that knowledge, experiences, and meanings are themselves created and continually re-created through different interactions between people and objects.³⁷ Charles West's early medieval prosthesis user was made independent, for example, but in a different environment and with different social interactions, say that of the arena war and in its aftermath, that user could be disabled. Indeed, particular properties, such as "assistive," are not inherent to the objects themselves but are constructed.

Just as studies of Western orthodox medicine have demonstrated the historically contingent nature of knowledge and experience through tools then, studies of disability's materiality have aided deeper understandings of how devices constructed the very categories of disability and impairment. Indeed, the design and volume of artificial legs that catered for unprecedented numbers

34 Heidi Hausse, *The Malleable Body: Surgeons, Artisans, and Amputees in Early Modern Germany* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2023); Pamela H. Smith, *From Lived Experience to the Written Word: Reconstructing Practical Knowledge in the Early Modern World* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2022); Smith, *The Body of the Artisan: Art and Experience in the Scientific Revolution* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004).

35 Gemma Almond, "Why the Anonymous and Everyday Objects Are Important: Using the Science Museum's Collection to Re-write the History of Vision Aids," *Sci. Museum Group J.* 13 (2020), <https://dx.doi.org/10.15180/201306/001>; Gemma Almond-Brown, *Spectacles and the Victorians: Measuring, Defining and Shaping Visual Capacity* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2023); Graeme Gooday and Karen Sayer, "Purchase, Use and Adaptation: Interpreting 'Patented' Aids to the Deaf in Victorian Britain," in Jones, *Rethinking Prostheses in Anglo-American Commodity Cultures* (n. 31), 48–69.

36 Raman Srinivasan, "Technology Sits Cross-Legged: Developing the Jaipur Foot Prosthesis," in Ott, Serlin, and Mihm, *Artificial Parts, Practical Lives* (n. 30), 327–47.

37 Beth Linker, "On the Borderland of Medical and Disability History: A Survey of the Fields," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 87, no. 4 (Winter 2013): 499–535.

of injured men in need of rehabilitation were not simply radically altered by the American Civil War and the two world wars, but expanded eligibility and thus the definition of disability as such legs increasingly became standard issue.³⁸ In interwar Britain, data sets used to establish standards of normal hearing were artificially elevated by the telephone system, which increased the number of people considered to have hearing loss.³⁹

The third example of how objects/materials embodied lay knowledge of health, healing, and well-being is print and visual culture. Influenced by early modern cultural historians like Robert Darton and Roger Chartier, who themselves were influenced by cultural anthropology as a founding discipline of material culture studies, historians of medicine have increasingly shown how text and images, ranging from medical textbooks and catalogues to recipe books, popular health books, and ephemera, were dynamic objects with an important role in knowledge making across a range of audiences.⁴⁰

Central to this material approach is its focus not only on content (ideas), but also on production and the physical traces left on the material by its compilers and viewers, such as notes and signatures, all of which contribute to the making (and remaking) of such objects and of health-related knowledge. The shabby condition of and annotations in certain popular health books and the newspaper clippings that accompanied them demonstrate the centrality of these books to domestic medicine in modern Anglo-America; doctors' inscriptions in nineteenth- and early twentieth-century British medical textbooks and their removal of medical instrument illustrations from instrument catalogues (to send medical companies) demonstrate how writing, reading, and ordering supplies formed part of everyday medical knowledge making and practice; and the neat characters printed on fine watermarked paper, clear organization of text, and a sober border style on printed flyers conveyed the authenticity of Scutellio, the early modern Venetian empiric physician, distinguishing him from charlatans whose flyers depicted crude woodcuts in red print.⁴¹

38 Lisa Herschbach, "Prosthetic Reconstructions: Making the Industry, Re-making the Body, Modelling the Nation," *Hist. Workshop J.* 44 (1997): 22–57; Mary Guyatt, "Better Legs: Artificial Limbs for British Veterans of the First World War," *J. Design Hist.* 14 (2001): 307–25; Julie Anderson, *War Disability and Rehabilitation in Britain: "Soul of a Nation"* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2011); Heather R. Perry, *Recycling the Disabled: Army, Medicine, and Modernity in WWI Germany* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2014); Roger Cooter, "The Disabled Body," in *Companion Encyclopaedia of Medicine in the Twentieth Century*, ed. Roger Cooter and John Pickstone (London: Routledge, 2002), 367–84.

39 Coren McGuire, "The Categorisation of Hearing Loss through Telephony in Inter-war Britain," *Hist. Technol.* 35, no. 2 (2019): 138–55.

40 Mary E. Fissell, "Hairy Women and Naked Truths: Gender and the Politics of Knowledge in 'Aristotle's Masterpiece,'" *William and Mary Quart.* 60, no. 1 (2003): 43–74. For photographs as dynamic objects, see Beatriz Pichel, "From Facial Expressions to Bodily Gestures: Passions, Photography and Movement in French 19th Century Sciences," *Hist. Hum. Sci.* 29, no. 1 (2016): 27–48; Beth Linker, "Shooting Disabled Soldiers: Medicine and Photography in World War I America," *J. Hist. Med. Allied Sci.* 66, no. 3 (2011): 313–46.

41 Charles Rosenberg, "Health in the Home: A Tradition of Print and Practice," in *Right Living: An Anglo-American Tradition of Self-Help Medicine and Hygiene*, ed. Rosenberg (Baltimore: Johns

Circulation and audiences are also key to this material approach. As Adrian Johns has argued “far from the meaning of a book being fixed by the printing press . . . [it is] something arrived at constructively, different communities pursuing interpretative conventions specific to their time and place.”⁴² Indeed, texts and images did not solely circulate among their intended audiences; textbooks could be, and indeed were, read, kept, and stored by lay audiences, just as medical practitioners read, kept, and stored popular forms of text.⁴³ Recipe making was both a practice and a product of knowledge making among early modern men and women, and accordingly historical focus on recipe books has challenged the persistent association of early modern household medicine with solely women.⁴⁴ Some early modern texts and images, including anatomical fugi-tive sheets and flap books, could elicit a range of unexpected responses from public audiences, such as titillation. Others were thought to have a direct impact on the health of the viewer; images of saints were thought to transmit God’s healing power, perfect figures in anatomy books were thought to imprint on the seed of both parents during reproduction, and a degree of warmth was thought to transmit to the body of the viewer of an image of fire.⁴⁵ Ongoing and varied social interactions with everyday objects and materials then make and remake knowledge and practices of health, healing, and medicine.

Spaces, Places, and Environments

The spaces in which objects of medicine and health were located also shaped and were shaped by knowledge and practice in historically contingent ways. Indeed, the technologies highlighted by Schlich that were vital for controlling surgical risk were likely to hold different sets of meanings beyond the nineteenth-century hospital operating theater. Of course, spatial approaches have always formed part of the archaeological method on which medievalists

Hopkins University Press, 2003), 1–20, 2; Claire L. Jones, “Re-reading Medical Trade Catalogs: The Use of Professional Advertising in British Medical Practice, 1870–1914,” *Bull. Hist. Med.* 86, no. 3 (2012): 361–93; Jones, *The Medical Trade Catalogue in Britain, 1880–1914* (London: Pickering & Chatto, 2013); Sabrina Minuzzi, *The Invention of the Author: The Privilege in Renaissance Venice* (Venice: Marsilio, 2017). See also the special issue of *Nuncius* on “Printing Medical Knowledge: Vernacular Genres, Reception and Dis-semination,” 36, no. 2 (June 2021); Elaine Leong, “Learning Medicine by the Book: Reading and Writing Surgical Manuals in Early Modern London,” *BJHS Themes* 5 (2020): 93–110.

42 Adrian Johns, “Natural History as Print Culture,” in *Cultures of Natural History*, ed. N. Jardine, J. A. Secord, and E. C. Spary (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996), 106–7.

43 Rebecca Whiteley, *Birth Figures: Early Modern Prints and the Pregnant Body* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2023); Whiteley, “Roy Porter Student Prize Essay: Figuring Pictures and Picturing Figures: Images of the Pregnant Body and the Unborn Child in England, 1540–c.1680,” *Soc. Hist. Med.* 32, no. 2 (2019): 241–66.

44 Elaine Leong, *Recipes and Everyday Knowledge: Medicine, Science, and the Household in Early Modern England* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018).

45 Frances Gage, *Paintings as Medicine in Early Modern Rome: Giulio Mancini and the Efficacy of Art* (University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press, 2016); see also Cavallo, “Objects” (n. 28).

and early modernists draw. In the absence of written records, the burial sites, hospitals, monasteries, and domestic buildings in which prophylactic and healing objects are found have revealed much about who used them and how.⁴⁶ But the increasing focus on medical material culture coincides with a revitalization of spatial approaches, which provides new insights into the ways in which objects and sites are inextricably connected and confer meaning on each other.

Like histories of lay objects, recent spatial studies have demonstrated that objects within traditional sites of professional medicine like hospitals and asylums did not always embody medical knowledge or represent medical power; knowledge and power could sit elsewhere. Ordinary beds and chairs could represent patient comfort in interwar Belgium hospitals, bed-side tables containing precious possessions demonstrated patient agency, while toothbrushes, lipsticks, cigarettes, and shoes held in hospital storage rooms suggested patient neglect and forgetfulness.⁴⁷ Everyday objects were adapted for particular medical spaces. Interwar beds at Brussels' Institute of Psychiatry of the Brugmann Hospital, for example, were made with full panels at the head and base, unlike those in other hospital departments that had bars, as a way of preventing suicide attempts.⁴⁸

The meanings of beds, tables, chairs, and toothbrushes within medical institutions then could be quite different from their meanings elsewhere, and scholars have drawn on the theme of "domesticity," as "a shared set of cultural practices encompassing relationships, behaviours, and things," to demonstrate how the nonmedical influenced the medical in such spaces.⁴⁹ Indeed, while initial studies of domesticity highlighted how professional medicine used domestic objects and interior design to transform an institution into the ideal of a middle-class home in an attempt to control and civilize working-class patients, recent studies, such as those by Eli Anders on nineteenth-century

46 For example, Geoff Egan, "Material Culture of Care for the Sick: Some Excavated Evidence from English Medieval Hospitals and Other Sites," in *The Medieval Hospital and Medical Practice*, ed. Barbara S. Bowers (London: Routledge, 2007), 65–76.

47 Valérie Leclercq and Veronique Deblon, "The Material Culture of Caring and Cur-ing," in *Medical Histories of Belgium: New Narratives on Health, Care and Citizenship in the Nine-teenth and Twentieth Centuries*, ed. Joris Vandendriessche and Benoît Majerus (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2021), 244–80; Marianna Scarfone, "Lives in Storage: Clothes and Other Personal Effects as a Way of Recovering Patients' Histories in a Psychiatric Hospital," in *Material Cultures of Psychiatry*, ed. Monika Ankele and Benoît Majerus (New York: Columbia University Press, 2020), 300–334. See also Monika Ankele, "The Fabric of Seclusion: Textiles as Media of (Spatial) Interaction in Isolation Cells of Mental Hospitals," in Ankele and Majerus, *Material Cultures of Psychiatry*, 140–58; J. L. Bazar, "Objects of Daily Life: Materiality in North American Institutions for the Insane" (Ph.D. diss., York University, 2013).

48 Majerus, "Material Objects in Twentieth Century History of Psychiatry" (n. 9), 161.

49 Jane Hamlett, *At Home in the Institution: Material Life in Asylums, Lodging Houses and Schools in Victorian and Edwardian England* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015). See also Inga Bryden and Janet Floyd, *Domestic Space: Reading the Nineteenth-Century Interior* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1999); Deborah Cohen, *Household Gods: The British and Their Possessions* (New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Press, 2006).

convalescent homes, demonstrate the importance of patient agency. Patients sometimes rejected the material trappings of middleclass life; moreover, maintaining a veneer of domesticity was often unsustainable and unaffordable for the home itself.⁵⁰

The material features of institutions' outdoor spaces, ranging from the grottos and summer houses of elite nineteenth-century lunatic asylums to Florence Nightingale's courtyard gardens and rural sites used for hydropathy, could be purposefully produced, designed, and curated to embody, represent, and produce medical knowledge and treat patients. Clare Hickman, for example, has demonstrated how doctors' gardens in the eighteenth century were cultivated to become crucial sites in the development and exchange of medical knowledge.⁵¹ But within institutions, material features could have other embodiments and representations. While it is well known that the high beamed ceilings, high windows, and long galleried corridors of the nineteenth-century pavilion hospital were designed according to Florence Nightingale's visions for airy wards, the appearance of an up-to-date surgical room could be a rhetorical device to persuade staff and patients that treatment was the most advanced available.⁵² Being able to fund and having the space to house cutting-edge technologies at the Royal Victoria Hospital in Montreal in the interwar period became a key factor in dissipating professional tensions between academics and practitioners once the University and Pathological Institute merged.⁵³ And far from suggesting the superiority of psychiatry knowledge Palgrave Handbook of the History of Surgery (n. 2), 261–82; Adams, "Designing a Discipline: and treatment, the battered and worn-out furniture that was a common feature of twentieth-century psychiatric hospitals demonstrated institutional neglect."⁵⁴

50 Mary Guyatt, "A Semblance of Home: Mental Asylum Interiors, 1880–1914," in *Interior Design and Identity*, ed. Susie McKellar and Penny Sparke (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2004), 48–71; Stephen Soanes, "'The Place Was a Home from Home': Identity and Belonging in the English Cottage Home for Convalescent Psychiatric Patients, 1910–1939," in *Residential Institutions in Britain, 1725–1970: Inmates and Environments*, ed. Jane Hamlett, Lesley Hoskins, and Rebecca Preston (London: Pickering & Chatto, 2013), 109–23; Claudia Soares, "A 'Permanent Environment of Brightness, Warmth, and "Homeliness": Domesticity and Authority in a Victorian Children's Institution," *J. Victorian Cult.* 23 (2018): 1–24; Carla Yanni, *The Architecture of Madness* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2007); Eli Anders, "'So Delightful a Temporary Home': The Material Culture of Domesticity in Late Nineteenth Century English Convalescent Institutions," *J. Hist. Med. Allied Sci.* 76, no. 3 (2021): 264–93.

51 Clare Hickman, *Therapeutic Landscapes: A History of English Hospital Gardens since 1800* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2013); Hickman, *The Doctor's Garden: Medicine, Science and Horticulture in Britain* (New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Press, 2021), 2.

52 Anmarie Adams and Thomas Schlich, "Design for Control: Surgery, Science and Space at the Royal Victorian Hospital, Montreal, 1893–1956," *Med. Hist.* 50, no. 3 (2006): 303–24; Schlich, "Surgery, Science and Modernity: Operating Rooms and Laboratories as Spaces of Control," *Hist. Sci.* 45, no. 3 (2007): 231–56; James Hopkins, "The (Dis)assembling of Form: Revealing the Ideas Built into Manchester's Medical School," *J. Hist. Med. Allied Sci.* 75, no. 1 (2020): 24–53.

53 Anmarie Adams, "Surgery and Architecture: Spaces for Operating," in Schlich, *Architecture for Pathology in the Interwar Period*, in Nott and Harris, *Making Sense of Medicine* (n. 11).

54 Chaney, "Psychiatry's Material Culture" (n. 9).

Thus, as is increasingly recognized, function does not inevitably shape form, and alternative interpretations have outlined the ways in which architecture is an iterative process whereby form shapes function. For example, Alistair Fair suggests that Johns Hopkins Hospital was a significant site for testing different ideas about ventilation.⁵⁵ Architectural histories have also identified the continued use of buildings and spaces long after the medical theories and associated practices have fallen out of favor, demonstrating the significance of factors such as cost to a building's materiality.⁵⁶

New sensory approaches to medical institutions, often explicitly engaged with material approaches, also offer multiple perspectives of knowledge and experience. Of particular note is Victoria Bates's recent study on the importance of the sight, sound, smell, and feel of various surfaces and objects in shades of the color white in shaping the British National Health Service (NHS) hospital. Resembling work common to material culture studies, Bates demonstrates how the hospital's continued use of white had multiple and layered diachronic and synchronic mean-ings: It could be a mechanism to control germs and create asepsis within the pharmacy, a strategy to create the impression of hygiene in the form of textured paint, a symbol of care in the form of a tea cup, a means of promoting rest through the reduced glare of a white or off-white ceiling, a signifier of power in the form of the white coat, and a sign of disrepair or disorder in the form of the "wall wound" or soiled bed linen. Bates's focus on continuity, rather than change, through multiple layers of mean-ing disrupts traditional narratives that emphasize the NHS as a turning point in British health care, but also adds fine-grain detail to everyday experiences often ignored by hospital historians, thus providing a useful model for those studying other institutions and contexts.⁵⁷

The home itself was, of course, a key material site in the production, practice, exchange, circulation, and consumption of health-related knowledge. Homemade medicines, domestic medical kits, health manuals, recipe books, and catalogues, in addition to everyday objects transformed into tools of healing, are all indicative of householder knowledge, acquisition, and practice.⁵⁸ But far from being conducive only to health, the materiality of

55 Alistair Fair, "A Laboratory of Heating and Ventilation: The Johns Hopkins Hospital as Experimental Architecture, 1870–1890," *J. Architecture* 19 (2004): 357–81.

56 Lisa Pfueller Davidson, "The Persistence of the Pavilion Plan: Three Hospitals at the Turn of the Twentieth Century," *Vernacular Architecture Forum*, June 4, 2016.

57 Victoria L. Bates, "Cold White of Day: White, Colour, and Materiality in the Twentieth-Century British Hospital," *Twent. Cent. Brit. Hist.* 34, no. 1 (2023): 1–37. See also Bates, *Feeling Blue: Colour and the Modern British Hospital* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2025).

58 Marion Baschin, "'Globules at Home': The History of Homeopathic Self-Medication," *Soc. Hist. Med.* 29, no. 4 (2016): 717–33; Claire L. Jones, "Under the Covers? Commerce, Contraceptives and Consumers in England and Wales, 1880–1960," *Soc. Hist. Med.* 29, no. 4 (2016): 734–56; Elaine Leong, "Making Medicines in the Early Modern Household," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 82 (2008): 145–68; Hilary Marland and Jane Adams, "Hydropathy at Home: The Water Cure and Domestic Healing in Mid-Nineteenth-Century Britain," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 83, no. 3 (2009): 499–529; Roberta Bivins, Hilary Marland, and Nancy Tomes, eds., "Histories of Medicine in the Household: Recovering Practice and

modern homes could also be dangerous, poisonous, and dirty and could carry germs and cause allergies, eczema, and asthma as well as psychological diseases.⁵⁹ From at least the 1950s, feminist writers depicted homes as sites of oppression, neurosis, and decay. The boundaries of the home were porous; just as all manner of objects and goods, as well as doctors and other historical actors, could be brought into the home for health and healing purposes, so too could they be transferred to hospitals and other spaces, highlighting an unending flow of people and things into and beyond the household. As Graham Mooney has highlighted, the domestic objects of Edwardian tuberculosis patients—baths, reclining chairs, and bed rests—not only resulted in the emergence of particular forms of domestic material consumption but also bridged the therapeutic divide between institutional and domestic space.⁶⁰ Along with objects then, material spaces, places, and environments were important in shaping knowledge, practices, and experiences of health, healing, and medicine through different forms of social interaction.

Consumption, Globalism, and Colonialism

Although originally used to depict the range of medical services available in early modern England, the conceptual space of the “medical market-place” has been a particular focus of historians keen to analyze objects as commodities.⁶¹ Indeed, much recent literature already discussed on everyday objects of health, domesticity, and institutions intersects with themes of commercialism and consumption. Middle-class trappings of the early modern Italian home, devices for the nineteenth-century convalescent and the Edwardian tubercular patient, and essentials for early modern domestic medicines entered the institution or home from the commercial sphere and, in doing so, shifted the identities of those within it from patients to consumers. As Mooney has argued, the encouragement of a culture of possession by producers, marketeers, and doctors meant that Edwardian tubercular patients were drawn into the realm of mass consumerism. As such studies make clear, commerce has never been deferential to science or medicine, and in practice the distinctions between scientific and commercial knowledge were often blurred.

“Reception,” *Soc. Hist. Med.* 29, no. 4 (2016): 669–75. For the history of science, see Simon Werrett, *Thrifty Science: Making the Most of Materials in the History of Experiment* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2019); Donald L. Optiz, Staffan Bergwik, and Brigitte Tiggen, eds., *Domesticity in the Making of Modern Science* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015).

59 Mark Jackson, “Homes Sweet Home: Historical Perspectives on Health and the Home,” in *Health and the Modern Home*, ed. Jackson (New York: Routledge, 2007), 1–17.

60 Graham Mooney, “The Material Consumptive: Domesticating the Tuberculosis Patient in Edwardian England,” *J. Hist. Geog.* 24 (2013): 152–66. See also Mooney, *Intrusive Interventions: Public Health, Domestic Space, and Infectious Disease Surveillance in England 1840–1914* (Rochester, N.Y.: University of Rochester Press 2015).

61 Mark S. R. Jenner and Patrick Wallis, “The Medical Marketplace,” in Jenner and Wallis, *Medicine and the Market in England and Its Colonies* (n. 18), 1–23.

Tracing the ways in which particular objects moved in and out of their commercial state through various stages of appropriation, historians of medicine have highlighted different geographical and chronological contexts, far extending commercial histories and anthropologies of the 1980s and 1990s that were limited to the fashionable consumption of medicines among the well-to-do of England and the contemporary consumption of material culture.⁶² Such studies have demonstrated how objects were not just imbued with medical knowledge but were also commodities (through processes such as advertising, patenting, and consumption) then personal belongings; and then everyday objects (that could be kept, used, or informally exchanged).⁶³ The value of an object and its benefit for the parties involved in the exchange varied with each transaction, and so too did the meaning of the object. Unsurprisingly, mass consumption in twentieth-century America has been a key focus, but so too has consumption within the industrial and industrializing economies of early modern and modern Europe. Accordingly, we know how patent medicines, prosthetic limbs, hearing aids, steel trusses, and walking sticks, for example, were (and are) material commodities that circulated various local, national, and global markets, interacting with the individual, the body, the state, the medical profession, and industry.⁶⁴

Spheres of commercial exchange have also been useful in making national, international, and global connections and, in particular, in shedding new light on imperialism, colonialism, and postcolonialism. Drawing on broader histories that have rejected outdated diffusionist perspectives on Western medical science, historians of medicine have outlined the role of desirable goods and materials as “tools of empire” that exploited indigenous populations in their production.⁶⁵ For example, focusing on the clothing made by British

62 John Brewer and Roy Porter, eds., *Consumption and the World of Goods* (London: Routledge, 1993); Appadurai, *Social Life of Things* (n. 5); Daniel Miller, *Material Culture and Mass Consumption* (Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1987).

63 Sara Pennell, “‘All but the Kitchen Sink’: Household Sales and the Circulation of Second-Hand Goods in Early Modern England,” in *Modernity and the Second-Hand Trade: European Consumption Cultures and Practices*, ed. Jon Stobart and Ilja van Damme (London: Springer, 2010), 37–56.

64 Nancy Tomes, *Remaking the American Patient: How Madison Avenue and Modern Medicine Turned Patients into Consumers* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2016); Tomes, *The Gospel of Germs: Men, Women and the Microbe in American Life* (Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press, 1998); Tomes, “‘Skeletons in the Medicine Closet’: Women and ‘Rational Consumption’ in the Inter-War American Home,” in Jackson, *Health and the Modern Home* (n. 59); Rima D. Apple, *Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture* (New Brunswick, N.J.: Rutgers University Press, 1996); Takahiro Ueyama, *Health in the Marketplace: Professionalism, Therapeutic Desires, and Medical Commodification in Late-Victorian London* (Palo Alto, Calif.: Society for the Promotion of Science and Scholarship, 2010); Jones, *Rethinking Prostheses in Anglo-American Commodity Cultures* (n. 31); Guffey and Williamson, *Making Disability Modern* (n. 32); Liliane Hilaire-Pérez and Christelle Rabier, “Self-Machinery? Steel Trusses and the Management of Ruptures in Eighteenth-Century Europe,” *Technol. Cult.* 54, no. 3 (2013): 460–502.

65 Elizabeth M. Collingham, *Imperial Bodies: The Physical Experience of the Raj 1800–1947* (Oxford: Polity, 2001); Anne McClintock, *Imperial Leather: Race, Gender and Sexuality in the Colonial Contest* (London: Routledge, 1995); Timothy Burke, *Lifebuoy Men, Lux Women: Commodification, Consumption, and Cleanliness in Modern Zimbabwe* (Durham, N.C.: Duke University

companies Jaeger and Burberry's and the Tabloid-brand medicine chests of Burroughs Wellcome and Co. (BW&C), Ryan Johnson demonstrates how the large market for goods that preserved white European health in Britain's colonies was intertwined with the late Victorian and Edwardian economic and political interests of empire. As Johnson shows, the contents of BW&C's medicine chests were not particularly innovative or novel and drew on long-standing indigenous materials and knowledge that the British sought to exploit and replace. But when promoted and circulated in Britain's African colonies, these chests contributed to a discourse of tropicality, a belief in Western progress and white European superiority through, for example, their covering with images of perceived racial differences.⁶⁶ The specific properties of the fabric of tropical clothing, designed to mimic "Black" skin, not only aimed to maintain well-being in intemperate climates in line with ambiguous notions of tropical medicine but also were significant in promoting a new and distinctive identity of would-be colonial adventurers. As Johnson also suggests, cultures are not discrete bounded entities but are dynamic, in constant contact and exchange through commodities. BW&C's medicine chests and tropical clothing are material evidence of an ongoing process of spatial and temporal hybridization between people and things continually forging new identities.

Also aligning with this view, other histories of medicine with specific concerns about knowledge making have challenged simplistic and deterministic notions of medical colonial power by emphasizing a negotiation between materials, healing cultures, colonized, and colonizer bound up in local cultures of meaning. Western medical objects and materials, including the stethoscope, watches, microscopes, and pharmaceuticals, were successfully refashioned and appropriated into local health care markets.⁶⁷ Local druggists in colonial India, for example, popularized imported therapeutic products alongside locally manufactured therapies that varied in price, quality, and processing and packaging techniques in order to appeal to both Western settlers and local populations.⁶⁸ Focusing on the eighteenth-century East and West Indies, Pratik Chakrabarti demonstrates the emergence of a new distinct hybridized medical material culture. Shaped by commerce, activity on

Press, 1996); Anne Gerritsen and Georgio Riello, eds., *The Global Lives of Things: The Material Culture of Connections in the Early Modern World* (London: Routledge, 2016); Catherine Hall and Sonya O. Rose, eds., *At Home with the Empire: Metropolitan Culture and the Imperial World* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006). For an alternative view of the influence of colonized over colonizer, see Marcy Norton, "Tasting Empire: Chocolate and the European Internalization of Mesoamerican Aesthetics," *Amer. Hist. Rev.* 111, no. 3 (2006): 660–91.

66 Ryan Johnson, "European Cloth and 'Tropical' Skin: Clothing Material and British Ideas of Health and Hygiene in Tropical Climates," *Bull. Hist. Med.* 83 (2009): 530–60; Johnson, "Tabloid Brand Medicine Chests: Selling Health and Hygiene for the British Tropical Colonies," *Sci. Cult.* 17, no. 3 (2008): 249–68.

67 Projit Bihari Mukharji, *Doctoring Traditions: Ayurveda, Small Technologies and Braided Sciences* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2016).

68 Nandini Bhattacharya, *Disparate Remedies: Making Medicines in Modern India* (Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press, 2023), 18.

plantations, and Western and indigenous medical knowledge, this new culture gave objects multiple meanings simultaneously: Therapeutics encapsulated the intellectual and material resources of conquest, while commerce transformed these commodities into profit and natural history enlisted them as objects of knowledge.⁶⁹ Such studies then emphasize a hybridization of medical and lay knowledge forged in new medical cultures in colonized lands through materials.

Future Directions

Focusing on objects ranging from instruments to domestic furnishings, and on material sites ranging from colonial India to hospital wards, material histories of health and medicine to date have provided nuance to progressive histories of medical knowledge and social control. Most significantly, such histories have demonstrated the hybridization of different medical cultures and the ongoing creation of new ones. And clearly, despite claims that the “material turn” is over, there are no signs of material histories of medicine abating; in fact, more case studies have the potential to uncover contingent and relational meanings of knowledge and practice in underexamined periods and locations and among different social groups. Indeed, while other disciplines like archaeology have long viewed the value of material sources for uncovering invisible or underrepresented social groups, historians of medicine are only just beginning to extend their focus beyond the profession and the consuming middle classes.

Further studies could center on the materiality of everyday health. As Sandra Cavallo has argued, early modern historians of medicine have so far concentrated on only two categories of talisman: those meant to facilitate reproduction and childbirth (as outlined earlier) and those intended to guard against plague. Further research on talisman, gems, stones, and even animal parts could highlight professional and vernacular knowledge of their healing properties and demonstrate how such objects were used to keep passions at bay, banish sadness, and work against rage.⁷⁰

But there is also much potential to challenge long-standing narratives of medical knowledge through closer study of the objects of professional medicine. Aligning with user-centric approaches in the history of technology, greater focus on objects that failed to work as intended and why, their continued use and reuse, and their repair and imitation would be beneficial to understanding how more kinds of materials shape knowledge, practice,

69 Pratik Chakrabarti, *Materials and Medicine: Trade, Conquest and Therapeutics* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2010). See also Geoff Bil and Jaipreet Viridi, eds., “Special Issue Introduction: Colonial Histories of Plant-Based Pharmaceuticals,” *Hist. Pharm. Pharmaceut.* 63, no. 2 (2022): 134–48; Anne Gerritsen and Burton Cleetus, eds., *Histories of Health and Materiality in the Indian Ocean World: Medicine, Material Culture and Trade, 1600–2000* (London: Bloomsbury, 2023).

70 Cavallo, “Objects” (n. 28).

emotions, experience, and identities, as well as transcending the innovation-centeredness of much of the history of medical technology.⁷¹

Moreover, there seems little reason (beyond practicality and preference) why histories cannot focus on both the professional and the everyday (or the professional everyday), given that all forms of materiality are relational. In fact, analyzing both professional and mundane forms of materiality together may have the effect of further breaking down boundaries between medicine and health care that were artificially constructed with the rise of professional medicine.

Expansion of the type of material site studied could also aid better understanding of the significance of a “natural” environment in shaping medical thought and practice. Certainly, as Jennifer Wallis has recently suggested in her discussion of British nineteenth-century hydropathic establishments, medical practitioners and resort proprietors successfully drew on the rhetoric of nature and combined it with mechanical novelty through their employment of compressed air baths, but there remains potential to further investigate the construction of “natural” environments, as well as their perceived role in health and healing.⁷² The discipline’s preoccupation with human actions may preclude such a focus, but further work on the significance of non-man-made environments and materials might be possible as environmental history/humanities gains traction and provides a further challenge to long-standing narratives equating spaces and places with medical progress or control.

Looking inward, historians of medicine’s embrace of the history of the body might aid further exploration of the living body as a material site. Indeed, as has long been recognized, human knowledge and experiences are ultimately grounded and enacted in the body (embodiment), which is, of course, material.⁷³ In addition to work on the significance of cloth-ing and adornment, a growing body of work on affect is providing new insights into the performative and material effects of emotions, ranging in focus from knowledge of material structures from John Hunter’s dis-eased heart to the

71 Ronald Kline and Trevor Pinch, “Users as Agents of Technological Changes: The Social Construction of the Automobile in the Rural United States,” *Technol. Cult.* 37 (1996): 763–95. Marjolijn Bol and E. C. Spary, eds., *The Matter of Mimesis: Studies of Mimesis and Materials in Nature, Art and Science* (Leiden: Brill, 2023) is a useful work on imitation in the history of science. Frank Trentmann, “Materiality in the Future of History: Things, Practices and Politics,” *Journal of British Studies* 48, no. 2 (2009): 283–307. Historians’ focus on innovation has been a long-standing bugbear of David Edgerton; see, for example, “Creole Technologies and Global Histories: Rethinking How Things Travel in Space and Time,” *J. Hist. Sci. Technol.*, no. 1 (Summer 2007), <http://www.johost.eu/?oidp2&actp&areap4&rip1&itidp>.

72 Jennifer Wallis, “A Machine in the Garden: The Compressed Air Bath and the Nine-teenth-Century Health Resort,” in *Histories of Technology, the Environment and Modern Britain*, ed. Jon Agar (London: UCL Press, 2018), 76–100.

73 Christopher Lawrence and Steve Shapin, *Science Incarnate: Historical Embodiments of Natural Knowledge* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998).

performativity of pain among patients suffering from hysteria and tetanus.⁷⁴ Likewise, drawing on Heidi Hausse's work on early modern prosthetic hands, historians of medicine might further examine how knowledge is constructed in the bodily acts of making and how these acts constitutes both persons and things.

But perhaps the most significant way historians of medicine might meaningfully engage with material culture is by being led by the materials and objects themselves, starting with analyses of their physical properties—weight, hardness, color, texture, taste, and smell—before moving outward to examine the specific themes in which they are already invested or new themes the objects/materials invoke.⁷⁵ As is already evident, historians of medicine are well aware that materiality is a process, but by remaining within their chronological specialisms, they generally do not connect the object's or material's various pasts with its present. Indeed, as David Edgerton has pointed out, historians are experts of particular contexts, not necessarily of particular technologies or things.⁷⁶ But accounting for an object or material in only one temporality means our knowledge of its significance is vastly incomplete. In following materials and objects, historians of medicine can engage with the *longue durée* of "material time," that is, following the object or material throughout its "life" from conception. Objects, the materials from which they are made, and other forms of materiality are, as one anthropologist suggested, "time travellers."⁷⁷

There are already a number of examples of "material time" on which to draw. Studies of the "after lives" of human remains from the nineteenth to the twenty-first centuries can provide insights into changing medical knowledge. For example, Hendrickson has chronologically traced the "after lives" of bones through the ways in which they were ground up and used in seventeenth-century drugs to their preservation and display for the study of

74 Irene S. Poplin, "Nursing Uniforms: Romantic Idea, Functional Attire or Instrument of Social Change?," *Nursing Hist. Rev.* 2, no. 1 (1994): 153–67; Nicole Baur and Joseph Mel-ling, "Dressing and Addressing the Mental Patient: The Uses of Clothing in the Admission, Care and Employment of Residents in English Provincial Mental Hospitals, c. 1860–1960," *Textile Hist.* 45, no. 2 (2014): 145–70; Jane Hamlett and Lesley Hoskins, "Comfort in Small Things? Clothing, Control and Agency in County Lunatic Asylums in Nineteenth- and Early Twentieth-Century England," *J. Victorian Cult.* 18, no. 1 (2013): 93–114; Bates, "Cold White of Day" (n. 57); Dolores Martín Moruno and Beatriz Pichel, eds., *Emotional Bodies: The Historical Performativity of Emotions* (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2019). Another excellent recent example is Michael Brown, *Emotions and Surgery in Britain, 1793–1912* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022).

75 Giorgio Riello, "Things That Shape History: Material Culture and Historical Narratives," in *History and Material Culture: A Student's Guide to Approaching Alternative Sources*, ed. Karen Harvey (London: Routledge, 2009), 24–47, 25; Laurel Thatcher Ulrich et al., *Tangible Things: Making History through Objects* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), 2.

76 Edgerton, "Creole Technologies and Global Histories" (n. 71), 83.

77 John Robb, "Material Time," in *The Oxford Handbook of History and Material Cultures*, ed. Ivan Gaskell and Sarah Anne Carter (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020), 122–39.

anatomy in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.⁷⁸ Victoria Bates's gesture to the layers of paint that have built up over time on the walls of twentieth-century British hospitals can be traced into the twenty-first century. And beyond the history of medicine, Sasha Handley's focus on the Countess of Derwentwater's bedsheet and her tracing of its meaning as a wife's memorial of her husband from the Jacobite uprising of 1715, its status as a holy relic within a nineteenth-century convent, and as an artifact within the mid-twentieth-century Stuart collection of the Museum of London highlights an object's continuous existence amid changing knowledge and practice.⁷⁹

The abandonment, or at least the expansion, of time-specific case studies to adopt "material time" may stretch a historian of medicine's contextual knowledge and methodological practice. However, Mary Fis-sell's much-anticipated book on the changing meaning and significance of Aristotle's *Masterpiece*, the Anglo-American bestseller on sex and reproduction, between the date of publication in 1684 and the twentieth century, might provide a subject-specific exemplar to follow I've yet to encounter elsewhere. And through material time, historians of medicine may not only provide a more complete picture of material significance but also find meaning beyond the period specific analytical categories to which they have become accustomed, such as hygiene, germ theory, science, disability, and indeed medicine itself. After all, objects can make us question the entire system of analytical categories that shape our discourse and lines of questioning.

If chronological abandonment seems like a step too far, moving from diachronic to synchronic analysis within a temporal context in order to trace multiple meanings across multiple social worlds simultaneously could be a way forward. Again, there are examples of this approach—for example, Bates highlights the multiple ways in which NHS hospitals used the color white. One way to undertake a diachronic analysis of this nature is the adoption of relational frameworks familiar to STS and anthropology, such as meshwork or entanglement, where temporality forms one of the key determinants of how actions unfold with people and things.⁸⁰ And crucially, as Schlich's network of control or Wailoo's technological system suggest, the adoption of such frameworks does not necessarily require giving agency to things as historians have generally feared. As already suggested, historians of medicine are beginning to at least outline relational frameworks for a single object. While Handley has traced the concomitant political, religious, and emotional

78 Marieke M. A. Hendricksen, "Objects," in *A Cultural History of Medicine in the Enlightenment*, ed. Elaine Leong and Claudia Stein (New York: Bloomsbury, 2021), 103–23. See also Samuel J. M. Alberti, *Morbid Curiosities: Medical Museums in Nineteenth-Century Britain* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011).

79 Sasha Handley, "Objects, Emotions and an Early-Modern Bed Sheet," *Hist. Workshop J.* 85 (2018): 169–94.

80 Ian Hodder, "The Entanglements of Humans and Things: A Long-Term View," *New Lit. Hist.* 45 (2014): 19–36; Hodder, *Entangled: An Archaeology of the Relationships between Humans and Things* (Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell, 2012).

meanings of Derwentwater's bedsheet in the eighteenth century, Johnson, for example, has highlighted how the tropical clothing that nineteenth- and early twentieth-century British colonizers wore could simultaneously embody knowledge of climate, signify meanings of comfort and commerce, and represent exploitation of those that sourced and made such items.

It might be then that instead of networks (with potentially problematic connotations), historians of medicine could start to think of a particular object or material as "a sort of organizing principle, a way to examine the tangled interactions that make up human history."⁸¹ Building on my own research on contraception, for example, historians of medicine might give far greater attention to materials like rubber, rather than solely the objects made from such materials.⁸² Viewing rubber as an organizing principle might enable the tracing of the processes of sourcing, production, global circulation, transformation, and commodification across multiple spaces, places, and social groups, thus allowing for simultaneous insights into global, colonial, institutional, commercial, and domestic contexts. Again, this is no small task, but examples from beyond the discipline might help. The recent work of cultural historian Christopher E. Forth, for example, has focused on the bodily tissue of fat as a material substance with a visceral presence, biological purposes (for example, lipids in terms of nutrition, and their value as a heat source), and cultural values in terms of ambivalence and disgust.⁸³

Historians of medicine's inclusion of themselves into their narratives could also be key to connecting past and present in material time. Historians generally do not autobiographize, but the inclusion of more critical self-awareness into history writing not only may allow us to better address materiality but could be essential to reinvigorating history as a powerful political force.⁸⁴ Indeed, by acknowledging their positionality, historians may be able to question the constructed constraints on, and the possibilities for, their own thinking around material culture. After all, the meanings of materiality we seek to trace are highly subjective and unstable, dependent not only on historical context but also on the historian's own experiences, ideologies, and position in the contexts of, among others, biomedicine, climate emergency, and a material-obsessed world in which people view improvement through the ever-greater consumption of things.

81 For his approach to entanglement with porcelain, see Robert Finlay, *The Pilgrim Art: Cultures of Porcelain in World History* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2010), 11.

82 Claire L. Jones, *The Business of Birth Control: Contraception and Commerce before the Sexual Revolution* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2020).

83 Christopher E. Forth, *Fat: A Cultural History of the Stuff of Life* (London: Reaktion, 2019); Forth, "The Qualities of Fat: Bodies, History, and Materiality," *J. Material Cult.* 18, no. 2 (2013): 135–54.

84 Roger Cooter and Claudia Stein, "The New Poverty of Theory: Material Turns in a Latourian World," in *Writing History in the Age of Biomedicine*, ed. Cooter (New Haven, Conn.: Yale University Press, 2013), 206–24. This is a critique of Patrick Joyce, "What Is the Social in Social History?," *Past and Present* 206, no. 1 (2010): 213–48. See also Claudia Stein, "Introduction," in Leong and Stein, *Cultural History of Medicine in the Enlightenment* (n. 78), 8.

There has been some wariness of autobiographizing, as there has been of materiality. Such wariness may be due to historians' discomfort with the lack of fixed meaning in both approaches, which call into question historians' authority, training, and separation of themselves from the sources they study in much the same way that Foucault's push for a history of the present did in the late twentieth century.⁸⁵ Unlike the turn toward illness narratives in the medical humanities, Anglo-American historians "prefer to draw a sharp and inherently evaluative distinction between their historical practices and the discussion of its premises."⁸⁶ This wariness is apparent from Iona McCleery's recent edited volume *A Cultural History of Medicine in the Middle Ages*. McCleery's introduction highlights the importance of reflexivity, stating that all authors reflected on who they were before writing their chapters because such features "affect how we do our research but are often not acknowledged enough," but few reflexive insights explicitly appear within the volume's chapter on objects.⁸⁷ Other historians of medicine are concerned that the inclusion of personal experiences will lead to new and different forms of power relations through a privileging of the author's voice, a voice that also needs to be critically reflected upon; yet those critical reflections add yet more layers of analysis and thus potentially take us further away from our subjects of interest.⁸⁸ And yet, there are examples in the history of medicine that embrace an approach that combines material analyses with personal reflections, thus connecting past and present in a politically engaged way. Of particular note is Jaipreet Virdi's recent history of modern Anglo-American deafness cures. Centering much of her history on innovation in hearing aids and technological fixes, Virdi deftly weaves in her (often emotive) personal story of deafness and hearing aid experiences with those of nineteenth- and twentieth-century hard-of-hearing individuals, doctors, and entrepreneurs, demonstrating "the myriad experiences of deafness and hearing impairment built on a foundation of many layers and threads of historical analysis."⁸⁹ More specifically, placing her own voice into her materially focused history demonstrates the ways in which deafness—and disability more broadly—is and was "an oppression of

85 Trentmann, "Materiality in the Future of History" (n. 71), 288.

86 Cooter, *Writing History in the Age of Biomedicine* (n. 84), 11; Angela Woods, "Beyond the Wounded Storyteller: Rethinking Narrativity, Illness and Embodied Self-Experience," in *Health, Illness and Disease: Philosophical Essays*, ed. Havi Carel and Rachel Cooper (London: Taylor & Francis, 2014), 113–28.

87 Iona McCleery, ed., *A Cultural History of Medicine in the Middle Ages* (London: Bloomsbury, 2021), 1–19; Gemma L. Watson and Roberta Gilchrist, "Objects: The Archaeology of Medieval Healing," in McCleery, *Cultural History of Medicine*, 107–29.

88 C. J. Millard, "Using Personal Experience in the Academic Medical Humanities: A Genealogy," *Soc. Theory Health* 18 (2020): 184–98; Sarah Chaney, "Am I a Researcher or a Self-Harmer? Mental Health, Objectivity and Identity Politics in History," *Soc. Theory Health* 18 (2020): 152–68. And more broadly, see J. W. Scott, "The Evidence of Experience," *Critical Inquiry* 17, no. 4 (1991): 773–97.

89 Jaipreet Virdi, *Hearing Happiness: Deafness Cures in History* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2020), 18.

difference rather than an impairment.” Central too to Viridi’s study is both her recognition that her deafness shapes the history she tells, and her explicit acknowledgement of her role as historian despite her initial reticence: “I am trained to distance myself from past actors, to remain objective and view sources through methodological rigor.”⁹⁰ The material and personal combined then provide powerful insights into dynamic knowledge making on numerous levels.

It is no coincidence that Viridi focuses on deafness given both disability history’s turn to the material and the nature of contemporary cultural Deaf activism in challenging past and present ableism.⁹¹ But further addressing how materials have embodied different kinds of knowledge in other historical areas relating to contemporary medical and social inequalities—race, reproductive rights, colonization, for example—not only might increase our understanding of how, why, when, and by whom such injustices were constructed but also could better enable us to challenge both these injustices and the simplistic narratives that surround them.⁹² Indeed, despite Western medicine’s many advances across the centuries, its materiality reminds us that knowledge, power, experience, and meaning were and are multilayered, produced in particular contexts and thus can be changed.

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⁹⁰ *Ibid.*, 17.

⁹¹ There has been a particular focus on the Deaf community’s rejection of the cochlear ear implant as a medical intervention. For example, see Stuart Blume, *The Artificial Ear: Cochlear Ear Implants and the Culture of Deafness* (New Brunswick, N.J.: Rutgers University Press, 2010). See also Catherine Kudlick, “Disability History: Why We Need Another Other,” *Amer. Hist. Rev.* 108, no. 3 (2003): 763–93.

⁹² Beyond medical history, see D. Chakrabarty, “History and the Politics of Recognition,” in *Manifestos for History*, ed. K. Jenkins, S. Morgan, and A. Munslow (Abingdon: Routledge, 2007), 77–87.